

Membership in farmers' organizations and intention to innovate: A mixed random utility and behavioral approach

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Abstract

Despite a growing body of literature on the adoption of agricultural innovations, their uptake by smallholder farmers in developing countries is slow. The processes underpinning farmers' decision-making in these countries are yet to be fully understood as the existing literature remains contradictory with regards to the factors explaining innovation adoption. Conflicting conclusions emerge from studies on different countries, which may be the result of different social, cultural, and institutional environments. We develop a novel theoretical model which joins random utility and behavioral models, to assess how membership in farmers' organizations affects intention to innovate. Using a two-steps framework, we assume that background factors influence farmers' attitudes, which in turn affect their intention to innovate. Three distal attitudes are selected as intermediate drivers: interest in new ways of production, attitude toward risk, and trust towards organizations promoting innovations. Membership in farmers' organizations is assumed to work as a mediator variable between background factors and intention to innovate. We test our framework using primary survey data from five African countries, 4,529 farmers, and more than twenty farmers' organizations. We find that behavioral attitudes work as mediator variables between the factors classically used in random utility models (e.g., farm, household, and farmer characteristics) and the intention to innovate. The effect of membership varies across organizations, and a specific institutional approach is necessary to evaluate which characteristics of a farmers' organization can impact the innovation behavior of its members.

Keywords: Africa; random utility; behavioral factors; innovation adoption; farmers' cooperatives; farmers' associations; risk; trust.

1. Introduction

Despite a growing body of literature on the adoption of agricultural innovation, the uptake of agricultural innovations by smallholder farmers in Africa is slow (Meijer et al., 2015), and far from ubiquitous (Kaliba et al., 2018). Furthermore, the processes underpinning farmers' decision-making in developing countries are yet to be fully understood, as the existing literature remains contradictory with regards to the factors that explain innovation adoption (Adnan et al., 2017a).

Most of the extant research has been conducted in specific national or regional contexts. Nevertheless, assessing the external validity of recognized factors across countries and cultures is necessary (Dessart et al., 2019). Indeed, conflicting conclusions frequently emerge from studies in different countries, and this may be the result of different social, cultural, and institutional environments; it is thus crucial to identify the interactions among these factors (Feder et al., 1985) in driving the intention to innovate.

One of the factors frequently discussed is the role of membership in farmers' organizations¹. Many authors include it among the drivers of innovation adoption. The specific causal mechanism linking organization memberships to innovation is interpreted in different ways and may include: i) a spillover effect (Manda et al., 2020), where "production practice used by the majority of members is likely to be adopted by other members" (Adnan et al., 2017c); ii) the credit and information provision guaranteed or facilitated by organizations (Manda et al., 2020), which is trusted more than other sources (Nwankwo et al., 2009); iii) the pooling of resources to develop economies of scale (Kolade and Harpham, 2014); iv) the role of extension officers, donors and non-governmental organizations which reach farmers' organizations members more easily than isolated individuals (Chagwiza et al., 2016; Okafor and Okafor, 2017).

Literature reviews focused on specific typologies of farming innovations are a good starting point to assess if membership in farmers' organizations really foster innovation. Prokopy et al. (2008) reviewed 25 studies on the adoption of management practices in the USA, finding that participation in organizations was positively correlated with adoption in seven studies, negatively correlated in one study, and not correlated in eight studies. Knowler & Bradshaw (2007) reviewed twenty-three studies about conservation agriculture around the world, finding that participation in organizations was positively correlated with adoption in two studies and not correlated in one study (the other studies did not consider memberships among the variables).

Many empirical papers have assessed the relationship between participation in farmers' organizations and the adoption of innovation in African countries. Some focus on this relationship as the main objective of the study, while others include organization membership among many potential drivers. Among the papers that specifically focus on organization membership we can mention Manda et al. (2020), which concluded that cooperative membership increases the speed of adoption of improved maize varieties in Zambia; Kolade and Harpham (2014), where cooperative membership is found to have a higher impact than other socioeconomic factors such as land access, gender, and educational status, on farmers' uptake of technological innovations in Southwest Nigeria; Okafor and Okafor (2017), which demonstrate that cooperative members adopt more agricultural technologies than non-members in Nigeria; and Chagwiza et al. (2016), which showed that cooperatives facilitate technological transformations among dairy smallholders in Ethiopia.

Many other papers include organization membership among the variables potentially explaining innovation without it being the main focus. Some found a positive correlation; others have identified no significant relationship. The cases where a positive correlation has been found include, among others, the adoption of new rice varieties in Sierra Leone (Mansaray et al., 2019); soil and water conservation practices (Nkegbe and Shankar, 2014) and maize production technologies in Ghana (Abawiera Wongnaa et al., 2018); bio-security measures against avian-influenza outbreaks among poultry farmers in Nigeria (Oladipo et al., 2020);

¹ In this paper we use "organizations" as a generic term in the introductory chapter, since most of the literature does not clearly differentiate among different kinds of institutional settings, like "associations" and "cooperatives". However, the distinction between specific institutional settings will become explicit in the empirical chapters, where we focus on actual organizations from our case study areas.

sustainable soil management practices among fluted pumpkin producers in Nigeria (Olowa et al., 2019); and crop technology packages in Ethiopia (Tefera et al., 2020).

The innovations for which the authors did not identify any significant correlation with membership in farmers' organizations include the adoption of aquaculture technologies among smallholder fish farmers in Kenya (Obiero et al., 2019); improved maize varieties (Takam-fongang et al., 2019) and technology maize packages in Cameroon (Mabah Tene et al., 2013); and improved maize varieties in Ethiopia (Zeng et al., 2018). In the case of cage tilapia farming in Ghana, Mantey et al. (2020) observed that membership has no correlation with adoption but is negatively correlated with disadoption.

Thus, empirical studies show that membership in organizations is not always a driver of innovation adoption. In fact, despite their many potential benefits, organizations may suffer from several problems including low managerial capacity, free riding, corruption, or mismatches between individual and collective interests (Chagwiza et al., 2016), and this can affect their capacity to foster innovation.

Furthermore, farmers' organizations can have very different objectives and can be tailored to serve different needs of their members, including production, purchasing, marketing, socialization, and information-exchange services (Adnan et al., 2017c). Chagwiza et al. (2016) distinguish between "marketing" cooperatives, and "livelihoods" cooperatives (specialized in the provision of public goods). For this reason, the effects of cooperative membership are mixed and context specific. This could also be due to governance characteristics, for example less or more centralized structures (Peng et al., 2018).

In turn, membership in organizations is not independent from the characteristic of the farmers and can be seen as the result of several drivers. Most of the factors driving membership according to the literature coincide with those normally associated with the adoption of new technologies, and include age, gender, education, household size, land ownership, access to off-farm income, and contacts with extension agents (Manda et al., 2020). For Chagwiza et al. (2016), the probability of joining a cooperative is higher among older (more risk-averse), more educated, and larger farmers. In a different study, Yahaya et al. (2019a) found that membership in a cooperative and adoption of rice intensification technology are both influenced by other variables such as the age, gender, and educational level of the respondents.

Most of the papers considered above adopt methodologies derived from the random utility approach to test the impact of several background factors (including membership in organizations) on innovation adoption. In the latest years, these approaches have been variously modified and enriched including behavioral drivers. This paper tests an innovative approach that integrates random utility and behavioral models. Using a two-steps framework, we assume that background factors influence farmers' beliefs and attitudes, which in turn affect their intention to innovate. Membership in farmers' organizations is assumed to work as a mediator variable. The role of membership in specific organizations is also investigated. To test this model, we use primary survey data collected in five African countries, involving 4,529 farmers and more than twenty farmers' organizations.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows: the next section presents the literature review about the main approaches used to investigate innovation adoption; Section 3 illustrates the materials and methods, including the hypothesis development and the research model; Section 4 presents the research results; Section 5 offers a discussion of the research findings; Section 6 concludes and offers key reflections for researchers and policymakers.

2. Models for innovation

2.1. Expected or Random utility model

Most of the studies on the adoption of innovations in agriculture are based on a random utility framework (Adnan et al., 2017b), stipulating that decisions whether to adopt specific technologies are affected by the variables that influence the farmers' expected utility, including limited resources and constraints (Métouolé Méda et al., 2018). These studies usually analyze actual adoption, rather than the intention to adopt (Adnan et al., 2017b). Within this framework, a large set of factors may influence adoption: Knowler and Bradshaw (2007) listed 142 different variables that resulted to be statistically significant in at least one of 31 studies about the adoption of conservation agriculture around the world (membership in farmers' organizations was just one of the variables). These factors have been grouped in different ways by different scholars. Meijer et al. (2015) distinguished between (a) characteristics of the farmer, (b) characteristics of the external environment, and (c) characteristics of the innovation. Ainembabazi and Mugisha (2014a), on the other hand, consider the following classification: (a) resource endowments (e.g., land, labor, livestock, and farm equipment), (b) market access (e.g., credit and input and output markets), (c) risk and uncertainty, (d) topographic factors (e.g., slope, soil type and location of the farm), and (e) intellectual capital accumulators (e.g., education, experience and extension). Edwards-Jones (2007) categorizes factors as (a) farmer characteristics, (b) household characteristics, (c) farm structure, (d) social milieu, and (e) characteristics of the policy under consideration (in their paper, policy rather than technology, was considered).

A large number of studies have adopted the random utility approach in African farming contexts, focusing, among others, on the adoption of agricultural technologies for banana, coffee and maize in Uganda (Ainembabazi and Mugisha, 2014b); technology packages for maize production (Mabah Tene et al., 2013) and kernel extraction machines in Cameroon (Mbosso et al., 2015); climate-smart agricultural technologies in Zimbabwe and Malawi (Makate et al., 2019); conventional, organic and genetically modified cotton in Burkina Faso (Métouolé Méda et al., 2018); bio-security measures against avian-influenza outbreaks among poultry farmers (Oladipo et al., 2020) and sustainable soil management practices among pumpkin producers in Nigeria (Olowa et al., 2019); improved maize varieties in Cameroon (Takam-fongang et al., 2019), Sierra Leone (Mansaray et al., 2019), and Ethiopia (Zeng et al., 2018); improved potato varieties (Abebe et al., 2013) and crop technology packages in Ethiopia (Tefera et al., 2020); improved sorghum varieties in Tanzania (Kaliba et al., 2018); and cage tilapia farming (Mantey et al., 2020), maize production technologies (Abawiera Wongnaa et al., 2018), systems of rice intensification (Yahaya et al., 2019b), and conservation practices in Ghana (Nkegbe and Shankar, 2014).

2.2. Socio-psychological methods

Interest in socio-psychological methods in farming studies, sometimes known as behavioural approach (Burton, 2004), has been induced by discontent with random utility models since the variables used within that approach resulted often in non-significant coefficients and because the literature did not allow to find generalized and consistent patterns across studies (Adnan et al., 2017b; Borges et al., 2014; Daxini et al., 2019a).

Knowler and Bradshaw (2007) concluded their review on conservation agriculture highlighting that "there are few if any universal variables that regularly explain the adoption of conservation agriculture across past analyses" and that the focus should shift to the particular conditions of individual locales. They also stressed that difference in results can be explained by differences in the methods of statistical analysis (Knowler and Bradshaw, 2007). Prokopy et al. (2008) also reviewed 25 years of literature on best management practices in the USA and concluded that the variables more often (but not always) positively correlated with adoption are education level, capital, income, farm size, access to information, and social network access.

Behavioral factors include a wide range of socio-psychological mechanisms, such as cognitive, emotional, personal, and social processes (Dessart et al., 2019). Several theories and models stemming from sociological, psychological, and economic disciplines build on those elements.

Some socio-psychological approaches define frameworks to be adopted uniformly across studies, using, as constitutive elements, constructs built from questions measuring different motives, values, and attitudes of respondents (Burton, 2004). These methods, which are normally used to explain intention to adopt rather than actual adoption, include, among others, the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) (Ajzen, 1991), the Reasoned Action Approach (RAA), the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) (Davis, 1989), and the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use (UTAUT) (Venkatesh et al., 2003). Constructs adopted in these theoretical frameworks include attitude toward using technology, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control in the case of TPB; and perceived usefulness and perceived ease to use in TAM. Constructs considered in other models include self-identity, personal norms, personal moral obligations, and social group norms (Mills et al., 2017; Van Hulst and Posthumus, 2016; Venkatesh et al., 2003). All these constructs, and the survey instruments used to assess them, are generally technology-specific; in other words, the questions are tailored to understand farmers' attitudes towards specific innovations, rather than generic situations.

These approaches have increasingly been used to study acceptance of farm technologies. The TPB, for example, has been used to evaluate the adoption of a nutrient management plan in Ireland (Daxini et al., 2019b), sustainable agricultural practices in Malaysia (Adnan et al., 2017b) and different land use practices in South Korea (Poppenborg and Koellner, 2013). Van Hulst and Posthumus (2016), on the other hand, used RAA to assess the adoption of conservation agriculture in Kenya.

2.3. Mixed approaches

Burton (2004) noted that, quite frequently, empirical studies adopt econometric methods that mix assumptions and tools derived from both the random utility and the behavioral approaches. He argued that, by incorporating within the behavioral dimension other "aspects of the farm such as farm size, family structure, land quality, and so on, this general approach offers a far broader and arguably more realistic perspective of farmers' decision-making environments" (pp.363).

Examples of studies adopting this strategy, based on RAA and TAM, include Zakaria (2014), who assessed intention to adopt genetically modified crops in Ghana (RAA); Obiero et al. (2019), who assessed intention to uptake aquaculture technologies among fish farmers in Kenya (TAM); and McDonald et al. (2016), who studied grazing system technology adoption among dairy farmers in Europe (TAM).

The combination of behavioural approaches with random utility approaches goes beyond the application of standardized procedures (e.g., TPB, RAA, TAM) and can overcome some limitations that arise when just one theory is used (Adnan et al., 2017d). Adnan et al. (2017d) suggested that a link between economic factors and thinking processes² can open "a window for building an integrative theoretical framework bridging the gaps between theories" (pp 45). Similarly, Meijer et al. (2015) combined "extrinsic" (i.e., characteristics of adopters and the environment) and "intrinsic" (i.e., attitudes) factors but warned that "there is little understanding of how perceptions and attitudes are shaped by the various extrinsic factors". Van Hulst and Posthumus (2016) highlighted that it is essential to theorize how (and not only if) a factor has an influence on adoption.

In an attempt to build a framework that bridges between different behavioral approaches, Dessart et al. (2019), building on Flay et al. (2009), distinguished between distal behavioral factors, i.e., "higher-order, general macro principles, relatively remote from specific decision-making situations" (e.g., personality,

² The actual process of thinking whether to adopt, with all the bias and behavioural drivers that it entails.

motivations, values, beliefs, general preferences and objectives), and proximal behavioral factors, i.e., “micro variables directly or almost directly related to the focus of the decision-making” (e.g., perceptions of the relative benefits, costs, and risks associated with a particular technology). In the following, we will refer to this classification to facilitate the reading of our modelling strategy, which attempts to link elements from various approaches.

3. Methods and data

3.1. The theoretical model

In this paper, we will not postulate that all factors, intrinsic and extrinsic, affect intention to adopt directly, which would result in estimating a single equation, as much of the empirical literature does. Following Adnan et al. (2017d) and Meijer et al. (2015), we assume that background (extrinsic) factors influence farmers’ perspective, beliefs and attitudes (intrinsic factors), which in turn positively or negatively affect their intention to adopt innovation (**Figure 1**). However, these authors propose TPB as a reference for their behavioral approach, which entails the use of proximal behavioral factors, strictly related to specific innovations. On the contrary, we aim to explore the impact of distal behavioral factors, which could be used to explain indifferently the adoption of several typologies of innovations proposed to farmers (Dessart et al., 2019).

We selected three distal attitudes that we name “interest in new ways of production,” “attitude toward risk” and “trust towards organizations promoting innovations”³. Membership in farmers’ organizations was chosen as a fourth variable which could mediate between background (extrinsic) factors and the intention to innovate. In other words, as suggested by literature, participation in farmers’ groups is not exogenous, since this choice can be affected by the characteristics of the farm, the household, and the environment (Chagwiza et al., 2016; Manda et al., 2020).

The choice of the three mediating attitudes was based on literature as well as theoretical assumptions. Interest in new ways of production is generally associated to specific characteristics of the innovation on the one side, and the potential adopter on the other side. For Rogers (1995), the innovativeness of an individual is defined by the moment of innovation adoption, distinguishing people between innovators, early adopters, early majority, late majority, and laggards. Macours (2019) reviews how different characteristics and benefits of innovations (e.g., yield-increasing, cost-reducing, risk-reducing, quality-enhancing) can affect adoption. However, we are interested in a more general attitude toward innovation as a mediator variable, as assessed by Škodová Parmová and Novotná (2022). Thus, “interest in new ways of production” can be considered a generalized version of the “attitude toward using technology” commonly used in TPB and UTAUT approaches.

One’s attitude toward risk is frequently associated with intention to innovate. In this paper, however, our focus is not on specific decisions under risk (which would be a proximal behavior) but on a more general attitude of the farmer, assessed through a self-elucidation approach (Weber et al., 2002; Weber and Milliman, 1997; Zeweld et al., 2019). Literature suggests that people who are risk averse will be reluctant to invest in technology (Juma et al., 2010). Interpretation of the risks is subjective, and the literature has highlighted that, in developing countries, farmers’ risk attitudes can be influenced by several factors, including education, group membership, household size, and economic conditions (Feder et al., 1985). For

³ These attitudes were measured using a 5-point Likert scale and the following question: “How much do you agree with the following statements?”

- 1) I like to try new ways of producing on my farm.
- 2) I prefer to avoid taking risks when it comes to managing my farm interests.
- 3) Most organizations promoting innovations in agriculture can be trusted.

The scores assigned to statement 2 have been reversed in this paper in order to be more easily interpreted.

instance, poor Kenyan farmers are generally more risk averse (Juma et al., 2010). Other empirical studies, in turn, have found no correlation between risk attitude, on one side, and age, gender, education, household size or income, on the other side (Haile, 2007; Mosley and Verschoor, 2007). In the field of agricultural technology, Le Cotty et al. (2018) found no statistically significant link between risk aversion (measured through hypothetical experiments) and fertilizer use in Burkina Faso. On the contrary, Liu (2013) found that in China more risk averse farmers adopt genetically modified *Bacillus thuringiensis* cotton later than others, while Liu and Huang (2013) found that risk aversion is positively correlated with pesticide use by Chinese farmers.

Since many innovations available to African farmers are promoted by different kinds of organizations (e.g., extension services, governmental and international agencies, NGOs, research centers, etc.), it is important to take account of farmers' trust in such organizations⁴. The link between trust in institutions and innovation adoption by farmers has been considered by many recent studies. In particular, the literature focused on the role of extension services in Iran (Kavakebi et al., 2023), China (Fan et al., 2022), Poland (Zawojnska, 2010) and in the Organization of Eastern Caribbean States (Ganpat and Narine, 2015). Arbuckle et al. (2015) examined the relationship between farmers' trust towards environmental or agricultural interest groups as sources of climate information, and their climate change beliefs. Lv and Li (2023) measured how different sources of information affect the adoption of sustainable environmental practices. Dilleen et al. (2023) discussed how trust in social media and vendors impacts the adoption of smart farming technology.

The overall structure of the theoretical framework adopted in this paper, based on the above considerations, is shown in Figure 1. It includes two levels. The first level is given by Relations 1-4, which links background (extrinsic) factors to memberships in farmers' organizations and to the three distal attitudes described above. The second level is represented by Relation 5, which links the attitudes and membership (i.e., the dependent variables of Relations 1-4) to intention to innovate. The background factors in the first step of the model include some of the variables frequently used in random utility models: farmer characteristics (age, gender and education); household characteristics (number of adult members aged 14 or older, migration of any of the household members, extent to which remittances contribute to the household's welfare, share of income spent on purchased food, extent to which the household's food needs have been met);⁵ farm characteristics (total land size); and institutional characteristics (possession of a mobile phone as a proxy of access to information, access to informal loans and formal credit). Finally, location characteristics are synthesized by geographical dummies for the areas covered by our sample.

⁴ Trust is particularly relevant for our research, which derives from a project where the innovations are introduced to farmers by innovative firms, NGOs, or research organizations.

⁵ The last two variables were chosen as proxies of income since it was difficult to establish comparable cross-country income levels and because incomes tend to be underreported or misreported if asked directly.

Figure 1. The overall structure of the theoretical framework.

Intention to innovate is evaluated separately for five different innovations. In fact, five different questions were used in the survey for specific innovations⁶:

- 1) A new technology (without any specification) that can help overcome a limitation faced by the farmer (the farmers were previously asked which are the limitations they are facing).
- 2) An irrigation system that can increase yields.
- 3) A new crop with a higher nutritional content at parity of selling price.
- 4) A new crop with a higher selling price.
- 5) An agreement between farmers that allows them to sell their crop production jointly in exchange for a higher unit price (social innovation).

⁶ The five questions used to assess intention to innovate are as follows. All of them were assessed using a 5-point scale.

- 1) You are given the option to change your production activity by adopting a new technology (e.g., a new fertilizer, a new equipment/tool) that allows you to overcome a limitation you are facing: to what extent would you be interested in adopting this technological innovation? (NB: this question is asked immediately after the farmers are asked which are the limitations they are facing).
- 2) Imagine you are growing an irrigated crop and that a new irrigation system raising yields has been adopted in the area: to what extent would you consider introducing this technology in your farm?
- 3) You are given the option to change your production by introducing a new crop (e.g., an orphan crop, an improved vegetable line, or a novel local variety) with a higher nutritional content at parity of selling price and costs: to what extent would you be interested in adopting this new crop?
- 4) You are given the option to change your production by introducing a new crop (e.g., an orphan crop, an improved vegetable line, or a novel local variety) with a higher selling price at parity of costs: to what extent would you be interested in adopting this new crop?
- 5) Imagine you can sell your crop production jointly with the other farmers' crop production so as to sell them at a slightly higher unit price for the whole group, but you must align the variety you grow as well as the seeding and harvesting time with the group: would you sell your production jointly?

Relation 5 includes a further set of explanatory variables, namely the membership in specific associations or cooperatives. During data collection, many associations and cooperatives were identified empirically; however, only a subset of them was selected to be included in the model via a set of dummy variables. The selection procedure is explained in Section 3.2. The choice of including dummy variables for specific farmers' organizations in addition to a generic identifier of membership, was motivated by the results of previous literature, which returned mixed conclusions on the role of organizations, pointing to the need of considering the nature and characteristics of the organizations.

Our theoretical framework suggests that background factors in Relations 1-4 should not affect intention to innovate further. In other words, it is not the size of the farm, or the education of the farmer to affect the intention to innovate per se, directly: these variables act in an indirect way, through their effect on distal attitudes, and by influencing the decision to join a farmers' organization. For example, an educated farmer with a large farm could be more trustful toward organizations promoting innovation and could be more risk taking and, therefore, more inclined to accept innovations. However, we are aware that other attitudes, not included in this framework (e.g., moral, and environmental concerns, injunctive and descriptive norms, signaling motives, etc.) may affect this final decision. For this reason, we expect that background factors still play a role, not fully internalized by our mediating factors, in the intention to adopt innovation.

On the basis of previous empirical research in Africa (Adnan, Nordin, Rahman, et al., 2017a; Chagwiza et al., 2016; Makate et al., 2019a; Manda et al., 2020; Mansaray et al., 2019; Métouolé Méda et al., 2018; Zeng et al., 2018), the expected direction of the effects is indicated in Tables 1 and 2. Table 1 refers to Equation 1, i.e., the effects of background factors on memberships in farmers' associations. Table 2 refers to Equation 5, i.e., the effects of distal attitudes and membership on intention to innovate. Ex-ante assumptions are not indicated, on the contrary, for equations 2-4 since the literature does not provide enough evidence on the direction of the effect. These assumptions represent the hypothesis of our study, which will be tested empirically using data from five African countries.

Table 1. Expected effect of background factors on membership in farmers' organizations.

Variable	Variable description and measurement	Mean (st. dev.) or % observations	Expected effect on membership
<i>Farmer characteristics</i>			
Age	Age of household head in years	46.1 (14.6)	+
Female	Binary value = 1 if household head is female; 0 otherwise	Yes: 33.3%	?
Education	Educational level of the household head, from 1 = illiterate to 5 = more than secondary school	3.0 (1.1)	+
<i>Household characteristics</i>			
Adult members	Number of adult members in the farmer's household (aged 14 or older)	3.9 (2.2)	0
Migration	Binary value = 1 if any of the household members has migrated; 0 otherwise	Yes: 33.0%	0
Remittance contribution	Extent to which remittances contribute to the household's welfare: bounded integer (from 0 = not at all, to 5 = a lot)	0.5 (1.3)	0
Food/Income	Share of the income spent on purchased food: bounded integer [from 1 = A very limited part (less than 25%), to 5 = Almost all (from 75% to 100%)]	2.7 (1.4)	0
Food need	Extent to which the household's food needs have been met: bounded integer (from 1 = Yes, more than enough, to 5 = No, I experience serious food shortages)	2.9 (1.2)	?
<i>Farm characteristics</i>			
Size	Land size: hectares (in logarithmic form in the models)	3.1 ha (6.1)	+
<i>Institutional characteristics</i>			
Loan	Access to informal loans = 1 if yes; 0 otherwise	Yes: 15.5%	+
Credit	Access to formal credit = 1 if yes; 0 otherwise	Yes: 29.8%	+
Mobile	Possession of a mobile phone = 1 if yes; 0 otherwise	Yes: 94.6%	+

Table 2. Expected effect of membership and attitudes on intention to innovate.

Variable	Variable description and measurement	Mean (st. dev.) or % observations	Expected effect on intention to innovate
Membership	Farmer's membership in local farmers' organization = 1 if yes; 0 otherwise	Yes: 39.9%	+
Interest	Extent to which the farmer agrees to: "I like to try new ways of producing on my farm": Bounded Integer (from 1 to 5)	4.5 (1.1)	+
Risk acceptance	Extent to which the farmer agrees to: "I prefer to avoid taking risks when it comes to managing my farm interests." Bounded Integer (from 1 to 5; the scale is reversed in the analysis, so that higher values indicate higher risk acceptance)	2.7 (1.6)	+
Trust	Extent to which the farmer agrees to: "Most organizations promoting innovations in can be trusted." Bounded Integer (from 1 to 5)	4.0 (1.3)	+

3.2. Research cases

The analysis involved a total sample of 4,529 farmers distributed in ten rural areas from five African countries (see Table 3 for the distribution of respondents among areas): Ait Ouallal Bittit/Ait Yazem and Dir Beni Mellal in Morocco, Chebika and Fernana in Tunisia, Kilombero and Mvomero in Tanzania, Kamuli and Nakaseke in Uganda, Mukurweini and Kitui in Kenya. These areas are very different in terms of geographical size as well as environmental, institutional, economic, and agronomic characteristics. The choice was motivated by the need of establishing so-called "Food Hubs", i.e., regions whereby value chains stakeholders, primarily small farmers, could collaborate in the adoption of innovations to stimulate local diversified production in the framework of an international project.⁷ In most areas, annual crops are predominant, except for Dir Beni Mellal and Chebika, where olive trees are the main agricultural resource. Small-scale crop farmers from each area were recruited through random sampling, using a two-stage approach in case several villages from a large area were involved (i.e., first selecting a subset of villages and then a subset of farmers therein). The data collection took place between March and November 2021, depending on local climatic conditions and thus the agricultural calendar.

In all the areas it is possible to find forms of organization among farmers, motivated by different objectives and managed under different institutional frameworks, such as cooperatives or associations (listed in Table 3). In total, 1,809 farmers among those interviewed were members of at least one group, which represents 40% of the total. The area with the higher membership share is Mukurweini (Kenya), with 79% of the farmers interviewed being member of at least one group; the area with the lower share is Mvomero (Tanzania) with 6% of the farmers interviewed being members of one group.

Among the 450 cooperatives and associations named by the interviewees overall, we chose 21 to be included in the econometric model as dummies (Equation 5). The members of these 21 organizations are 730 in total, i.e., 40% of the farmers that are members of at least one association. In particular, 20 organizations were selected because they were those with the largest number of members in our sample (from 17 members, the least represented, to 112). Using this approach, all the ten areas were represented by at least one group, except for Ait Ouallal Bittit/Ait Yazem (Morocco) and Mvomero (Tanzania). In the case of Ait Ouallal Bittit/Ait Yazem, we decided to include the largest of the groups in the area, i.e., the Kharichfa Association, with twelve members in the sample. On the contrary, no group was selected for the Mvomero area, where the associative system seems to be poorly developed, and there are no groups with more than four members in the sample. The names of the associations or cooperatives chosen for the analysis, and their relative incidence on the sample from the local area, are found in **Error! Reference source not found.**, while Table A1 in Appendix provides a more detailed overview of their characteristics.

⁷ Name of the project omitted for review.

Table 3. List of areas and farmers' organizations chosen for the empirical model.

Country	Area	Interviewed	Members of associations	% members on sample	Farmers' Organizations	Number of members in the sample
Morocco	Beni Mellal	400	140	35%	ZITOUNE Coop. COLEZA Coop.	33 18
	Ait Ouallal Bittit	500	115	23%	KHARICHFA Association	12
Kenya	Kitui	482	252	52%	Neema self-help group	20
	Mukurweini	505	400	79%	Rugi farmer cooperative society	67
					New gikaru farmer cooperative society	112
					Rumukia farmers cooperative society	42
					Ruthaka farmers cooperative society	68
Wakulima cooperative society	72					
Tanzania	Kilombero	407	72	18%	Kidatu Sugarcane Growers Association (KSGA)	22
	Mvomero	504	31	6%	-	
Tunisia	Chebika	431	134	31%	GDA Karma	23
					GDA Jefna	19
	GDA Ayaycha	17				
Fernana	500	114	23%	SMSA	26	
				GDA Hrayer Gloub Thiren	44	
URAP	32					
Uganda	Kamuli	400	301	75%	Busiba cooperative society	22
					Twekembe Kamuli Busiba Coperative	22
					Edikokolima Saving and Credit Association	20
	Nakaseke	400	250	63%	Namasinda kwekulakulanya group	20
Nakaseke vegetable producers and seed multiplication association	19					
TOTAL		4529	1809	40%		730

4. Empirical approach

Two econometric approaches were used to test our assumptions: (1) separate estimation of the five Relations in Figure 1; (2) simultaneous estimation with generalised Structural Equation Models (generalised SEM; Rabe-Hesketh et al., 2004). For applying the first approach, we developed two datasets: one with one observation per farmer (4,529 in total) for estimating Relations 1, 2, 3, and 4; and one with five observations per farmer (22,645, i.e., one for each innovation)⁸ for Relation 5. For the simultaneous estimate we used a single dataset with one observation per farmer and treated the intention to adopt innovations as a latent construct inferred from the variables measuring intention to adopt the specific innovations. We assume that the latent variable is a common cause of the five intentions to adopt specific innovations; therefore, our model is a so-called "reflective SEM," which differs from the "formative SEMs," whereby the latent variable is instead a composite construct summarising the common variation of the observed indicators (Edward & Bagozzi, 2000). Besides the possibility of using latent variables, the advantages of SEM are that we address endogeneity (and thus correlation of the errors) through simultaneous estimation, and we avoid the "artificial" reduction of the standard errors caused by the five-fold multiplication of the sample size for Relation 5. A further advantage is that SEM allows estimation of indirect and total effects of the background factors (Baron & Kenny, 1986). By comparing the two approaches and discussing them jointly, we increase the robustness of our findings.

⁸ In this approach, the "Intention" to innovate is treated as a single dependent variable assuming five values for each farmer, potentially different (one for each innovation typology), and four dummies are included as additional explanatory variables to assess how each innovation typology impacts Intention (with the fifth innovation representing a baseline).

As a preliminary step, we implemented a logarithmic transformation of the land size to overcome the issue of skewness, and we checked all models for collinearity, detecting no issues in this regard. Since we assumed that receiving loans or credit, the share of income spent on food, and the level of food security were endogenous, we trialled instrumental variable estimation of the equations for distal constructs and for membership in cooperatives, using setbacks (income loss, job loss, farm cost increase, and food shortages) as instruments; however, the endogeneity tests were non-conclusive, and the instruments chosen resulted to be weak.

One of the model typologies most used in the literature on innovation adoption is logistic regression (Zeweld et al., 2019). This is an appropriate method when the dependent variable is binary or ordered categorical, like in our case. Therefore, for the first econometric approach (separate equations), we estimated one logit model (Relation 1) and four ordered logit models (Relations 2, 3, 4, and 5). For the second approach (SEM), we estimated the Relations 1, 2, 3, and 4 using the same model typology as above (respectively logit and ordered logit), while Relation 5 was estimated with a linear model, and the latent dependent variable (intention to innovate) was obtained endogenously.

The empirical form of Relations 2, 3, and 4 for farmer i is the following:

$$y_i^* = \mathbf{X}_i^T \beta_X + \mathbf{Y}_i^T \beta_Y + \mathbf{Z}_i^T \beta_Z + \varepsilon_i \quad (1)$$

Where y_i^* is an unobserved latent variable discretised by means of the Likert-scale,⁹ \mathbf{X}_i is a vector of farmer and household characteristics, \mathbf{Y}_i is a vector of farm economic characteristics, \mathbf{Z}_i is a vector of local characteristics (location dummies), β 's are the model coefficients, and ε_i is the error term. The ordered logit estimate also includes cutoff points for y_i^* to assume the discretised 1-to-5 values. In Relation 1, y_i^* is replaced by $\text{logit}(E[m_i | \mathbf{X}_i, \mathbf{Y}_i, \mathbf{Z}_i])$, where m_i is a dummy for cooperative membership.

In the estimation with separate equations, Relation 5 assumes the empirical form below:

$$y_{ik}^* = \beta_k + \beta_m m_i + \beta_A + \beta_N n_i + \beta_R r_i + \beta_T t_i + \mathbf{X}_i^T \beta_X + \mathbf{Y}_i^T \beta_Y + \mathbf{Z}_i^T \beta_Z + \varepsilon \quad (2)$$

Where k are the innovations, β_k are innovation-fixed effects, β_A is a vectors of association-fixed effects (each farmer can belong to more than one association) and y_i^* is, again, an unobserved latent variable discretised by means of the Likert-scale: the observed variable is the intention to innovate p_{ik} .

In the SEM estimate, Relation 5 assumes the following linear form:

$$P_i = \beta_m m_i + \beta_A + \beta_N n_i + \beta_R r_i + \beta_T t_i + \mathbf{X}_i^T \beta_X + \mathbf{Y}_i^T \beta_Y + \mathbf{Z}_i^T \beta_Z + \varepsilon \quad (3)$$

Where P_i is the latent intention to innovate, and innovation-fixed effects are excluded from the right side.

For robustness checks, because membership in specific associations entails membership in associations in general, we tested that the coefficients for m_i , and for membership in each association $\beta_{A_1}, \dots, \beta_{A_n}$ in turn, were jointly significantly different from zero. Also, because we assumed that \mathbf{X}_i and \mathbf{Y}_i impact p_{ik} (or P_i , depending on the estimation approach) both directly and indirectly through n_i , r_i , t_i and m_i (mediator variables), we calculated the indirect and the total effects (sum of direct and indirect effects) of these variables on p_{ik} and P_i , and whether these effects differed significantly from zero.

All the estimates were implemented using Stata15 (Stata Corp, 2017) and the *gsem* command for the generalised SEMs (Stata Corp, 2023).

5. Results

⁹ The observed ordered categorical variables are n_i for openness to new production methods, r_i for risk taking, and t_i for trust.

Descriptive statistics are reported in **Error! Reference source not found.** and **Error! Reference source not found.**. The results of the estimations, illustrated in Table 1 to Table 4, show that there are virtually no differences in the results obtained with the two estimation approaches, i.e., the separate equations (Table 1) and the generalized SEM (Table 2). Almost all the variables that are statistically significant with one approach are also significant (and with the same sign) with the other approach.

Many of the hypotheses made about membership in farmers' organizations (Relation 1, Table 1 and Table 2) are supported by our data. In fact, there is a positive (and statistically significant at the 5% level) relation between membership and: age¹⁰, education, land size, and access to formal and informal credit. Additionally, female farmers are significantly more likely to be members. The extent to which the household's food needs have remained unmet has, on the contrary, a negative sign, i.e., the farmers who experience food insecurity are less likely to be members.

For the dependent variable "Interest in new ways of production" (Relation 2, Table 1 and Table 2), we find a positive correlation with age¹¹, education, number of adult members, land size, share of the income spent on purchased food as well as the extent to which the food needs have remained unmet, suggesting that poorer and more food insecure farmers are more interested in new ways of production – possibly as a way to overcome their current challenges. A negative correlation is on the contrary found for the presence of emigrated household members – suggesting the presence of labor shortages reducing interest in innovation.

Risk acceptance (Relation 3, Table 1 and Table 2) is positively correlated with access to credit and the extent to which the household's food needs have remained unmet. A negative relationship is detected with age¹² and access to informal loans – which are indeed a less risky alternative to formal credit.

Finally, trust in organizations (Relation 4, Table 1 and Table 2) is positively correlated with age¹³, number of adult members, and access to informal loans, while negatively correlated with the presence of emigrated household members.

Most of the geographic dummies (reported in Appendix, Tables A2 for Relations 1-4, and Table A3 for Relation 5) also generate significant coefficients in the four Relations, suggesting that the location (and its specific socio-economic characteristics) matters but the direction is not trivial.

Regarding Equation 5 (Table 3), the two approaches use different assumptions to include the effect of the five innovation proposals. In the separate ordered logit model, each innovation is represented by a dummy which can yield a specific effect on the intention to adopt or not. In the SEM, the five innovations are considered as five observations driven by an "Intention" latent variable.

Despite this difference, the results obtained with the two approaches are identical in terms of the effect of the four mediating variables resulting from Relations 1-4. Interest in new ways of production, risk acceptance, and trust yield a positive and statistically significant (at the 1% level) effect on the intention to innovate in both models (separate ordered logit and SEM). On the contrary, the membership in (any) farmers' organizations, despite a positive sign, is non-significant, although at the margin (i.e., the probability that the coefficient differs from zero is 11%, in both models). We will focus on this aspect in the next Section.

In the ordered logit model (separate estimates), where the baseline is the intention to adopt "An unspecified new technology that can overcome a limitation faced by the farmer", the results indicate a positive effect on intention to adopt when the innovation is "A hypothetical irrigation system that can raise yields". On the

¹⁰ But negative for Age square, suggesting that the probability of being a member is inverted U-shaped, i.e., it increases up to a certain point and decreases for older farmers, *ceteris paribus*.

¹¹ But negative for Age square, suggesting that the openness to new ways of production increases up to a certain point and then decreases for older farmers, *ceteris paribus*.

¹² But positive for Age square, suggesting that the youngest and the oldest are more likely to accept risk.

¹³ But negatively for Age square, suggesting that the relationship is inverted U-shaped.

contrary, “A new crop with a higher nutritional content,” “A new crop with a higher selling price,” and “An agreement among farmers that allow to sell crop produce jointly” all yield a negative impact on the intention to innovate, compared to the baseline. As explained above, in the SEM, the effect of the single innovations on the intention to adopt is not measured within the structural model. Instead, all the five innovations are assumed to be the observed realizations of the latent variable “Intention,” as shown in the SEM measurement model (Table A4 in Appendix). The latent variable is found to have the largest impact on the intention to adopt a nutrient crop, followed by the joint sale of products, a more profitable crop and, at some distance, a new irrigation system – all positive and significant relationships. While these results seem to contradict those of the separate models, they actually confirm them, and are a consequence of the reflective nature of our SEM, whereby the latent construct influences the single intentions rather than being a combination of them. For instance, while the benefits for the farmer of adopting a highly nutritious crop are less visible, and confounding factors such as profit maximization are thus unlikely to drive intention, other innovations such as a more profitable crop might be appealing also to less innovative farmers, which reduces the relative share of variance explained by the latent construct.

5.1. Results for specific cooperatives and associations

The geographical dummies and the membership in specific associations and cooperatives (in addition to the membership in *any* organizations), included in Relation 5, also have a significant impact on the intention to innovate.

As previously explained, among the coefficient estimated for Relation 5, the membership in *any* farmers’ organizations is just below the 10% level of significance. However, this generic coefficient, which could be interpreted as the *average* impact of membership, does not consider the specific effect of being a member of one of the 21 farmers groups chosen for the estimation. This latter set of coefficients represents, instead, the effect of being a member of that specific organization *beyond* the basic effect of membership (which is common to all organizations). To evaluate the total effect of the generic membership and the specific effect of the membership in one organization, a joint test on the significance of the two variables was implemented. The results of this test are shown in Table 4. For specific farmers’ organizations, there is a significant effect on intention to innovate, although the direction is not univocal.

5.2. Effect of background factors

The model for Relation 5 includes the effects of background factors (the same included in Relations 1-4), to assess if they still yield a significant effect on the intention to innovate, or if their effect has been completely endogenized by the distal attitudes and the memberships in farmers’ organizations; or, adopting a different point of view, to assess how far the distal attitudes and the membership in organizations operate as mediator variables between background factors and intention to innovate (Table 3).

The results indicate that some background factors still play a significant role in explaining intention to innovate. In particular, land size, access to credit, possession of a mobile phone, and the extent to which the household’s food needs have remained unmet, yield a positive effect on intention. Age has a positive effect, while age square has a negative one (inverted U-shaped effect). In Table 3, it is possible to see the total effect of background factors calculated with the SEM, which includes the indirect effects mediated by attitudes and membership in organizations.¹⁴ It must be noted that, in most of the cases, the indirect effects are at least as significant as the direct effects, and for a few variables (i.e., education, number of adult members, migration,

¹⁴ The indirect effect sums up the indirect effects through all the mediator variables (three attitudes and membership).

loan) the total effect is mainly captured by the mediating variables, supporting our choice to include them as mediators in the theoretical model. We should also point out that except for the expenditure on food, whose indirect and direct effect go in opposite directions, yielding a non-significant total effect, the direct and indirect effects always go in the same direction (negative, or positive).

Table 1. Estimates of relations 1, 2, 3 and 4 using ordered logistic regression.

Variables	Membership (1)	Interest (2)	Risk acceptance (3)	Trust (4)
<i>Farmer characteristics</i>				
Age	0.0649 (0.0148) ***	0.0398 (0.0130)***	-0.0194 (0.0111)*	0.0470 (0.0111)***
Age square	-0.0004 (0.0001)***	-0.0005 (0.0001)***	0.0003 (0.0001)**	-0.0005 (0.0001)***
Female	0.2153 (0.0882) ***	-0.1076 (0.0809)	0.0914 (0.0666)	0.0641 (0.0662)
Education	0.1405 (0.0376) ***	0.0779 (0.0355)**	-0.0207 (0.0295)	-0.0112 (0.0295)
<i>Household characteristics</i>				
Adult members	0.0081 (0.0176)	0.0530 (0.0176)***	0.0047 (0.0140)	0.0442 (0.0140)***
Migration	0.1202 (0.1018)	-0.2691 (0.0980)***	-0.0471 (0.0825)	-0.1380 (0.0812)*
Remittance contribution	0.0394 (0.1294)	0.1448 (0.1244)	0.01300 (0.1023)	0.0252 (0.1019)
Food/Income	0.0308 (0.0298)	0.0803 (0.2716)***	0.0200 (0.0227)	0.0277 (0.0228)
Food need	-0.1572 (0.0334) ***	0.1107 (0.0312)***	0.1784 (0.0261)***	-0.0177 (0.0261)
<i>Farm characteristics</i>				
Size log	0.3356 (0.0663)***	0.1809 (0.0626)***	0.0375 (0.0523)	-0.0456 (0.0522)
<i>Institutional characteristics</i>				
Loan	0.8680 (0.1015)***	0.1500 (0.1058)	-0.1959 (0.0827)**	0.2851 (0.0826)***
Credit	0.2703 (0.0807)***	-0.0066 (0.0777)	0.1858 (0.0632)***	-0.0944 (0.0627)
Mobile	1,0394 (0.2039)***	-0.1529 (0.1534)	0.0964 (0.1306)	0.0358 (0.1300)
Prob > chi2	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
Pseudo R2	0.2473	0.0484	0.0992	0.0218
Log-likelihood	-2,293.3607	-3,926.817	-5,990.6907	-5,902.0503
Sample size	4,529	4,529	4,529	4,529

*10% level; **5% level; ***1% level

Table 2. Estimates of relations 1, 2, 3 and 4 using SEM.

Variables	Membership (1)	Interest (2)	Risk acceptance (3)	Trust (4)
<i>Farmer characteristics</i>				
Age	0.0649 (0.1478)***	0.0398 (0.0131)***	-0.0194 (0.0111)*	0.0470 (0.0111)***
Age square	-0.0004 (0.0001)***	-0.0005 (0.0001)***	0.0003 (0.0001)**	-0.0005 (0.0001)***
Female	0.2154 (0.08882)**	-0.1076 (0.0809)	0.0914 (0.0666)	0.0641 (0.0662)
Education	0.1405 (0.0376)***	0.0779 (0.0356)**	-0.0207 (0.0295)	-0.0112 (0.0295)
<i>Household characteristics</i>				
Adult members	0.0082 (0.01762)	0.0530 (0.0176)***	0.0047 (0.0140)	0.0442 (0.0140)***
Migration	0.1202 (0.1018)	-0.2691 (0.0976)***	-0.0471 (0.0825)	-0.1380 (0.0812)*
Remittance contribution	0.0394 (0.1294)	0.1448 (0.1244)	0.1300 (0.1023)	0.0252 (0.1020)
Food/Income	0.0308 (0.0298)	0.0803 (0.0272)***	0.0200 (0.0227)	0.0277 (0.0228)
Food need	-0.1572 (0.0334)***	0.1107 (0.0312)***	0.1784 (0.0261)***	-0.0177 (0.0261)
<i>Farm characteristics</i>				
Size log	0.3356 (0.0663)***	0.1809 (0.0626)***	0.0375 (0.0523)	-0.0456 (0.0520)
<i>Institutional characteristics</i>				
Loan	0.8680 (0.1015)***	0.1499 (0.1058)	-0.1959 (0.0827)**	0.2851 (0.0826)***
Credit	0.2703 (0.0807)***	-0.0067	0.1858 (0.0632)***	-0.0945 (0.0627)
Mobile	1.0394 (0.2039)***	-0.1529 (0.1538)	0.0964 (0.1306)	0.0358 (0.1299)

*10% level; **5% level; ***1% level; Sample size: 4,529. Log-likelihood (full generalized SEM): -50,634.439

Table 3. Estimates of relation 5 using ordered logistic regression and SEM, including indirect and total effects.

Variables	Ordered logit	SEM: Direct effect	SEM: Indirect effect	SEM: Total effect
<i>Attitudes and membership</i>				
Membership	0.0914 (0.0565)	0.0366 (0.0232)		
Interest	0.3900 (0.0241)***	0.1897 (0.0112)***		
Risk acceptance	0.0924 (0.0160)***	0.0381 (0.0059)***		
Trust	0.1924 (0.0172)***	0.0768 (0.0074)***		
<i>Innovations</i>				
Irrigation system	0.0686 (0.0404)*			
Joint sale	-0.7060 (0.0379)***			
Nutritive crop	-0.8992 (0.0370)***			
Profitable crop	-0.1620 (0.0385)***			
<i>Control variables</i>				
Age	0.0336 (0.0084)***	0.0143 (0.0033)***	0.0128 (0.0032)***	0.0271 (0.0045)***
Age square	-0.0004 (0.0001)***	-0.0002 (0.0000)***	-0.0001 (0.0000)***	-0.0003 (0.0000)***
Female	-0.0370 (0.0523)	-0.0010 (0.0196)	-0.0041 (0.0175)	-0.0055 (0.0260)
Education	-0.0017 (0.0211)	0.0036 (0.0087)	0.0183 (0.0081)**	0.0218 (0.0117)*
Adult members	0.0052 (0.0101)	0.0036 (0.0041)	0.0139 (0.0037)***	0.0176 (0.0055)***
Migration	-0.0156 (0.0623)	-0.0093 (0.0241)	-0.0591 (0.0206)***	-0.0684 (0.0316)**
Remittance contribution	0.0101 (0.0818)	0.0381 (0.0302)	0.0358 (0.0257)	0.0739 (0.0396)*
Food/Income	-0.0427 (0.01652)***	-0.0176 (0.0067)***	0.0193 (0.0057)***	0.0016 (0.0089)
Food need	0.0988 (0.0201)***	0.0404 (0.0078)***	0.0207 (0.0075)***	0.0611 (0.0107)***
Size log	0.0538 (0.0357)	0.0323 (0.0157)**	0.0445 (0.0153)***	0.0768 (0.0214)***
Loan	0.0627 (0.065)	0.0119 (0.0240)	0.0746 (0.0296)**	0.0865 (0.0367)**
Credit	0.0591 (0.0464)	0.0311 (0.0185)**	0.0084 (0.0172)	0.0395 (0.0250)
Mobile	0.2385 (0.0904)***	0.1046 (0.0381)***	0.0154 (0.0401)*	0.1200 (0.5452)**
Prob > chi2	0.0000			
Pseudo R2	0.0892			
Log-likelihood	-22,840.191			
Sample size	22,645			

*10% level; **5% level; ***1% level

Table 4. Role of organizations in intention to innovate: specific effects (only the coefficient estimated for the dummy) and total effect (joint significance of dummy and general membership in farmers' organizations).

Country	Area	Organization	Specific effect in separate models	Total effect in separate models	Specific effect in SEM	Total effect in SEM
Morocco	Beni Mellal	ZITOUNE Coop.				
		COLEZA Coop.				
	Ait Ouallal Bittit	KHARICHFA Association	++	+++	+++	+++
Kenya	Kitui	Neema self-help group				
		Rugi farmer cooperative society		+	++	+++
		New gikaru farmer cooperative society				
		Rumukia farmers' cooperative society				
		Ruthaka farmers' cooperative society				
	Mukurweini	Wakulima cooperative society		+		
Tanzania	Kilombero	Kidatu Sugarcane Growers Association				
		Mvomero	-			
Tunisia	Chebika	GDA Karma				+
		GDA Jefna	---	---	---	---
		GDA Ayaycha		+		+
	Fernana	SMSA				
		GDA Hrayer Gloub Thiren URAP	--	-		
Uganda	Kamuli	Busiba cooperative society				
		Kamuli Nankulyaku Maize cooperative	+++	+++		
		Edikokolima Saving and Credit Assoc.	+++	+++		
	Nakaseke	Namasinda kwekulakulanya group				

+; ++; +++: positive effects at 10%, 5% and 1%. -; --; ---: negative effects at 10%, 5% and 1%. Empty cells indicate no significant effect.

6. Discussion

This research used a mixed theoretical framework, where the impact on intention to adopt of the classical (background) factors included in expected utility models is mediated, and thus further “explained,” by a layer of attitudinal variables. Membership in farmers’ organizations, which is a farmer’s decision, is assimilated to a mediator. Several assumptions embedded in this framework are confirmed by the results.

Firstly, most background factors have a significant effect on membership in farmers’ organizations. In particular, the results confirm what emerged in the literature review by Manda et al. (2020) that age, education, access to liquidity (i.e., loans and credit) and social networks (i.e., mobile phone ownership) are associated with membership in organizations. However, our results indicate that female-headed households are more likely to be members of cooperatives than their male counterparts, which is the opposite of what Manda et al. (2020) stated; while the impact of the household size resulted to be non-significant from a statistical point of view. Some of the above-mentioned variables also have significant impact on the three distal attitudes considered (i.e., “interest in new ways of production,” “attitude toward risk,” and “trust towards organizations promoting innovations”).

Secondly, the three mediating attitudes are clearly correlated, in a positive way, with the intention to innovate. This confirms that: i) “interest in new ways of production” can represent a generalized version of the “attitude toward using technology” used in the TPB (Ajzen, 1991) and UTAUT (Venkatesh et al., 2003) approaches; ii) people who are risk averse are reluctant to invest in technology (Juma et al., 2010); and iii) trust in institutions is positively correlated with intention to innovate, as shown in previous studies (Fan et al., 2022; Kavakebi et al., 2023; Zawajska, 2010)

Thirdly, when controlling for the above attitudes as well as more classical variables, the (average) impact of the membership in farmers’ organizations on farmers’ intention to innovate is not significantly different from zero. In turn, we found that the membership in specific farmers’ organizations may yield positive or negative effects. This is discussed more in detail in Subsection 6.1 below.

Fourthly, for most background factors, a relevant share of their impact on intention to innovate is captured by the mediator variables. This means that the inclusion of attitudes and membership as mediator variables in our theoretical model improves the explanatory power of the background factors.

Fifthly, part of the effect of the background factors is not captured by the distal attitudes and by membership in organizations. This suggests that other attitudes might be considered for future multilevel models like this.

The results also indicate that the intention to adopt innovation is, unsurprisingly, related to the innovation type. Organizational innovations (such as coordination to sell products in a cooperative way) and innovations without a clear monetary benefit, such as the use of new varieties with higher nutritional value (at parity of selling price) are less likely to be accepted. However, the farmers who are more propense to adopt a specific innovation are also more propense to adopt the other innovations.

6.1. The role of specific organizations

Membership in specific farmers’ organizations can have either a positive or a negative effect on the intention to adopt innovation. The direction of the significant coefficients is summarized in Table 4, while a more detailed overview is provided in Table A5 in Appendix. Identifying organizations’ characteristics and elements

that can explain an intention to innovate goes beyond the objectives of this paper. However, some considerations could be drawn based on the knowledge of local experts and on informal conversations with members and managers of the organizations included in our sample, especially concerning the comparison of different organizations within the same country.

In Morocco, the three organizations included in the model have the same institutional structure. They are all cooperatives; furthermore, they have similar objectives and engage in similar activities such as pooling of resources, and storage and marketing of agricultural products. Thus, the reason for the positive effect associated to the Kharichfa Cooperative cannot be found in institutional differences but might be due to specific characteristics of the group or leadership. In particular, the leadership of this cooperative seems to have a great (positive) influence on the openness of its members and on their intention to accept technological innovations. The president of this cooperative is a retired agricultural advisor, and his deputy is also a member of the local administration. The members of the cooperative trust his decisions and the direction taken. Other aspects of potential importance to explain the good functioning of the Kharichfa Cooperative, and consequently, the trust in the innovations proposed by it, is the homogeneity of farmers and their common involvement in activities connected with irrigation and water saving.

In Kenya too, particularly in the Mukurweini area, cooperatives have a similar structure, and implement similar activities. This area is particularly suitable for coffee production, and cooperative participation is very common among farmers. The five cooperatives selected for this area all deal with coffee production, collection, and marketing, and all are owners of coffee factories. Thus, also in this case, organization-specific effects on the propensity to innovation of farmers might be linked to the intrinsic characteristics of each cooperative. Wakulima Cooperative and Rugi Farmers' Society are the two cooperatives yielding positive effects, while others do not generate any significant effect. Indeed, the members of these two cooperatives are pooling resources for investing in high quality coffee crops and high value-added technologies.

The Tunisian organizations included in our study are characterized by the GDA (Groupement de Développement Agricole, French acronym for Agricultural Development Groups) form, and by other models. Two GDAs (Jefna and Hrayer Gloub Thiren) are the only organizations in the sample that resulted in a negative effect on the intention to innovate. This could indicate that these GDAs are having performance problems and, consequently, their members are discouraged from innovating and investing. However, membership in other two GDAs (Ayaycha and Karma) yielded a positive effect; thus, the effects seem to be again the result of incidental situations inside the groups. In fact, many GDAs in Tunisia are still facing a wide range of financial, technical, and organizational constraints (Farolfi et al., 2022; Mahdhi et al., 2021).

Contrary to the previous countries, in Uganda, the farmers' organizations included in this survey encompass cooperatives and associations with different legal forms; thus, multiple factors could affect their role in fostering the intention to innovate. Two organizations yielded positive and significant effects. The first is Kamuli Nankulyaku Maize Cooperative produces, which processes and sells maize flour to big buyers outside the district. In 2022, this cooperative acquired technology support in the form of a free solar-powered irrigation system from the Ministry of Agriculture, Animal Industry and Fisheries. It also deals with savings and loans as one of its major activities. The fact that this cooperative is engaged in various business initiatives and is interested in large investments suggests its high willingness to innovate and is an indicator that members may be risk takers. The second organization is Edikokolima Saving and Credit Association, involved in maize shelling with their own machinery. This group does not share any association profit with members but use money either to loan members or to make investments. The chairperson declared that they have not yet reached the stability level at which they could share profits; they want to buy more assets and have more money available for loans. This approach could be a strong sign (and possibly a cause) of the higher intention to innovate shown by its members.

7. Conclusion

This study is based on a cross country survey conducted in five African countries, involving ten geographic areas and 4,529 farmers. An innovative approach that links random utility models and behavioral models has been used to assess if four variables work as mediators between the background factors normally adopted in random utility models (i.e., socio-demographic, and economic characteristics of the farmers, households, and farms) and the intention to adopt innovations. The four mediating variables included three behavioral attitudes related to risk, trust, and interest in innovation and, as a fourth variable, the membership in different types of farmers' organizations. Membership is thus considered an intermediate decision that, like purely behavioral attitudes, is explained by background factor and explains the intention to innovate.

While the papers based on the standard random utility model provide insights on *how* background factors affect intention to innovate, this study aspired to provide insights on *why* background factors affect the intention to innovate. In other words, we believe that factors such as land size and age cannot directly affect innovation propensity; if they do, it is only because they affect attitudes such as trust, openness to innovation, and risk propensity. However, it is to be clarified that, as always happens with cross-sectional models, the causality (direction) of these relationships cannot be tested and, consequently, cannot be assured. Causal relationships in this framework are based on assumptions, partially justified by related literature and logical inference.

Our results indicate that local conditions always affect behavioral attitudes, membership in farmers' organizations, and intention to accept innovation, which points to the importance of implementing cross-country studies with standardized methodologies, to verify if classical variables used in propensity to innovate studies have the same effect everywhere. The intention to adopt can also be affected by the type of innovation. This study, however, goes beyond typical behavioral approaches that study how specific (i.e., proximal) beliefs and attitudes, explicitly related to specific innovations, affects farmers' intention to accept these specific innovations (as done in TPB). Here, we considered more general (i.e., distal) behavioral factors, and evaluated their relationship with a more general, underlying intention to accept innovations.

Finally, the main goal of this paper was to make an advance on the question if and how membership in farmers' organizations is related to the intention to innovate. The extant literature provided mixed, results which could be affected by differences in the methodologies used for the analysis. This study applied the same methodology and theoretical framework over five countries and more than twenty farmers' organizations. The results (unsurprisingly) suggest that the effect of membership varies across organizations, and that a more specific institutional approach is necessary to evaluate which characteristics of a farmers' organization can affect the intention to innovate of its members.

Our study presents some limitations. First, we rely on one single observation per farmer at a specific point in time, and this cross-sectional nature of the dataset does not allow to determine the direction of causality. In the future, a longitudinal study could allow better understanding of whether, for instance, joining a cooperative increases the intention to adopt innovations, or vice versa. Second, we measure attitudes through statements in a survey rather than revealing them through incentivized experiments or by observing and recording actual behaviours. Third, we only focus on intention to adopt rather than actual adoption, which is subject to social desirability bias, i.e., the farmers might overstate their intention to adopt to please the interviewers since there are no direct consequences for their welfare; this will not necessarily result in adoption, although we expect the bias to go in the same direction for all farmers.

In the future, we could link background factors, membership in farmers' organizations, and attitudes, to actual adoption measured through randomized controlled trials conducted in a subset of locations in the same project and verify if intention to adopt aligns with actual adoption. Additionally, we could reveal behavioural traits such as attitude to risk and trust using incentivized experiments – this has been already

done in the project, but only in a subset of locations and for a significantly smaller sample size. Finally, future projects could adopt a longitudinal approach by contacting the same farmers at different points in time, thus overcoming some of the data limitations we faced.

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Appendix. Supplementary tables

Table A1. Characteristics of the farmers' organizations chosen for the empirical model

Area	Organization	Legal / Institutional framework	Objectives and activities
Dir Beni Mellal (Morocco)	ZITOUNE Cooperative	Law 112-12 concerning cooperatives in Morocco	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Pooling of resources and improving bargaining power and market access - Storage, development, and marketing of agricultural products
Dir Beni Mellal (Morocco)	COLEZA Cooperative	Law 112-12 concerning cooperatives in Morocco	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Pooling of resources and improving bargaining power and market access. - Storage, development, and marketing of agricultural products
Ait Ouallal Bittit (Morocco)	KHARICHFA Cooperative	Law 112-12 concerning cooperatives in Morocco	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Pooling of resources and improving bargaining power and market access. - Storage, development, and marketing of olive products
Mukurweini (Kenya)	Rugi farmers society	Cooperative Societies Act, Chapter 490 and SACCO Societies Act of 2008	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Farmers' training and seminars. - Coffee collection, milling and marketing. - Forster environmental conservative measures. - Provision of capital assistances to farmers. - Cushioning on risk related to perishable commodities
Mukurweini (Kenya)	New gikaru coffee growers' society	Cooperative Societies Act, Chapter 490 and SACCO Societies Act of 2008	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Farmers' training and seminars - Forster environmental conservative measures - Maintenance of coffee wet mills based on recommended standards. - Enhance Fairtrade standards. - Provision of capital finances to farmers. - Cushioning on risk related to perishable commodities. - Coffee collection and marketing. - Promotion of management of farming inputs.
Mukurweini (Kenya)	Rumukia farmers' cooperative society.	Cooperative Societies Act, Chapter 490 and SACCO Societies Act of 2008	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Coffee collection, processing, milling, and marketing. - Offer trainings on good agricultural practices.
Mukurweini (Kenya)	Ruthaka cooperative society	Cooperative Societies Act, Chapter 490 and SACCO Societies Act of 2008	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Coffee collection, milling and marketing. - Farmers' training and seminars - Forster environmental conservative measures. - Provision of capital finances to farmers. - Cushioning on risk related to perishable commodities.
Mukurweini (Kenya)	Wakulima cooperative society	Cooperative Societies Act, Chapter 490 and SACCO Societies Act of 2008	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Coffee and milk collection and marketing. - Promotion of management of farming inputs - Bargaining for coffee and milk market prices - Provision of capital finances to farmers - Cushioning on risk related to perishable commodities. - Farmers' training and seminars
Kitui (Kenya)	Neema self-help group	Mandated and operate under the Ministry of Gender, Children, and Social Development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Income generation. - Initiation and management of community wide projects.
Kilombero (Tanzania)	Kidatu Sugarcane Growers Association (KSGA)	Cooperative Societies Act No. 6 of 2016 (Chapter 112 of the laws of Tanzania) The Cooperative Societies Regulations, 2015 (GN. No. 272 of 2015)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To simplify the business transaction between the farmer and the investor (Kilombero mill) - Acting as guarantor for a loan on behalf of the farmer for cane production - Supervising all farm activities in the field, from production to harvesting - Providing training/technical advice through demo plots - Helping the farmer to receive subsidized farm input
Chebika (Tunisia)	GDA Jefna	Decrees n°87-1261, 27 October 1987 and rectified by the law n°2004-24, March 15, 2004.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Purchasing or producing (pumping) water - Water selling and distribution to adherents - Collection of water fees - Infrastructure maintenance of irrigated perimeter
Chebika (Tunisia)	GDA Karma	Decrees n°87-1261, 27 October 1987 and rectified by the law n°2004-24, March 15, 2004.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Purchasing or producing (pumping) water - Water selling and distribution to adherents - Collection of water fees - Infrastructure maintenance of irrigated perimeter
Chebika (Tunisia)	GDA Ayaycha	Decrees n°87-1261, 27 October 1987 and rectified by the law n°2004-24, March 15, 2004.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Purchasing or producing (pumping) water - Water selling and distribution to adherents - Collection of water fees - Infrastructure maintenance of irrigated perimeter

Fernana (Tunisia)	URAP (Regional Union of Agriculture and Fishing)	Agricultural union that represents professionals in the primary sector	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Organizing and representing farmers and fishers and to defend their interests - To protect their rights and to ensure the development of their assets.
Fernana (Tunisia)	GDA Hrayer Gloub Thiren	Decrees n°87-1261, 27 October 1987 and rectified by the law n°2004-24, March 15, 2004.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Organizing training/technical sessions through demonstration plots. - Facilitating women's access to subsidized agricultural inputs. - Assisting women in the processing and marketing of their agricultural products.
Fernana (Tunisia)	SMSA	Mutual agricultural service companies with variable capital and shareholders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Purchasing of raw materials and inputs - Conserving, transforming, storing, conditioning, transporting, and selling of agricultural products
Kamuli (Uganda)	Kamuli - Nankulyaku Maize cooperative society	Cooperative societies Act Chapter 112	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Producing, value adding and selling maize flour to big buyers outside the district. - Selling maize bran to members of cooperative that do poultry, piggery, and dairy farming at subsidized price. - Storing maize. - Savings and loaning as one of its major activities.
Kamuli (Uganda)	Edikokolima Saving and Credit Association	Self-Help Groups as defined under section 99 of the Tier 4 Microfinance Institutions and Money Lenders Act, 2016.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Using assets for profit (maize shelling machine and motorcycle) - Profits are invested in agriculture (cassava, maize, and tomatoes).
Kamuli (Uganda)	Busiba cooperative society	Cooperative societies Act Chapter 112	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Bulking and marketing produce collectively - Buying seeds from National Agricultural Research Organization (NARO) and producing quality declared seed that they sell to farmers - Providing training to farmers
Nakaseke (Uganda)	Nakaseke vegetable producers and seed multiplication association	Cooperative societies Act Chapter 112	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Exploring opportunities that come with working together with other farmers as a group - Trainings about quality of agricultural inputs
Nakaseke (Uganda)	Namasinda kwekulakulanya group	Cooperative societies Act Chapter 112	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Mainly saving and loaning members - Catering business - Hiring out tents and chairs for events - Grow, bulk and collectively market maize

Table A2. Role of locations in relations 1, 2, 3 and 4, in ordered logistic regression models and SEM.

Country	Area	Membership (1)	Interest (2)	Risk acceptance (3)	Trust (4)
Morocco	Dir Beni Mellal	0.1837 (0.1602)	0.5441 (0.1468) ***	-0.7258 (0.135) ***	0.2436 (0.1366) *
	Ait Ouallal Bittit	-0.3973 (0.1586) **	0.8703 (0.1423) ***	-0.9480 (0.1271) ***	-0.3448 (0.1246) ***
Kenya	Kitui	1.3128 (0.1708) ***	1.2700 (0.1643) ***	-1.6148 (0.1422) ***	-0.1784 (0.1401)
	Mukurweini	2.5260 (0.1849) ***	1.2501 (0.1664) ***	-2.3248 (0.1505) ***	0.0423 (0.1457)
Tanzania	Kilombero	-0.5111 (0.1869) ***	0.4948 (0.1494) ***	-1.7063 (0.1400) ***	-0.2950 (0.1387) **
	Mvomero	-1.2405 (0.2278) ***	0.9169 (0.1523) ***	-2.4164 (0.1405) ***	0.6505 (0.1392) ***
Tunisia	Chebika	(omitted)	(omitted)	(omitted)	(omitted)
	Fernana	-0.1562 (0.1641)	0.4131 (0.1456) ***	-0.0092 (0.1376)	0.2441 (0.1343) *
Uganda	Kamuli	2.2166 (0.1859) ***	3.0421 (0.2632) ***	-3.0043 (0.1658) ***	1.1266 (0.1574) ***
	Nakaseke	1.5326 (0.1787) ***	2.0957 (0.2025) ***	-2.2965 (0.1560) ***	0.2612 (0.1491) *

The results coincide between the separate models and SEM. The Chebika Food Hub has been omitted for collinearity. Significance: * 10% level; **5% level; ***1% level.

Table A3. Role of locations in Relation 5, in ordered logistic regression model and SEM.

Country	Area	Ordered logit	SEM
Morocco	Dir Beni Mellal	0.0654 (0.0427)	-0.1930 (0.0932) **
	Ait Ouallal Bittit	0.0337 (0.0394)	-0.2082 (0.0892) ***
Kenya	Kitui	0.2394 (0.0457) ***	0.2445 (0.1112) **
	Mukurweini	0.4539 (0.0613) ***	1.1930 (0.1876) ***
Tanzania	Kilombero	0.2391 (0.0454) ***	0.3229 (0.1084) ***
	Mvomero	0.2933 (0.0444) ***	0.5498 (0.1067) ***
Tunisia	Chebika	(omitted)	(omitted)
	Fernana	0.2196 (0.0417) ***	0.4996 (0.1128) ***

Uganda	Kamuli	0.5249 (0.0517) ***	1.5253 (0.1385) ***
	Nakaseke	0.4906 (0.0501) ***	1.2593 (0.1333) ***

The Chebika Food Hub has been omitted for collinearity. Significance: * 10% level; **5% level; ***1% level.

Table A4. SEM measurement model (correlation between the latent variable “Intention” and the intention to adopt specific innovations).

Variable	Coefficient	St. err.	z	P> z	95% conf. int.	
Generic new technology (baseline)						
Intention	1.0000	(constrained)				
Constant	2.4305***	0.1260	19.29	0.000	2.1835	2.6775
Irrigation system						
Intention	1.0910***	0.0382	28.55	0.000	1.0162	1.1659
Constant	2.2856***	0.1337	17.09	0.000	2.0235	2.5476
Joint sale						
Intention	1.3885***	0.0565	24.58	0.000	1.2778	1.4992
Constant	1.2579***	0.1619	7.77	0.000	0.9405	1.5753
Nutritive crop						
Intention	1.4558***	0.0591	24.63	0.000	1.3400	1.5716
Constant	1.1027***	0.1645	6.70	0.000	0.7802	1.4252
Profitable crop						
Intention	1.3172***	0.0518	25.41	0.000	1.2156	1.4188
Constant	1.7248***	0.1479	11.66	0.000	1.4349	2.0147

Sample size: 4,529. Significance: * 10% level; **5% level; ***1% level.

Table A5. Coefficients for membership in specific organizations, and significance levels (Relation 5).

Country	Area	Organization	Ordered logistic model			Generalized SEM		
			Coeff. (st. err.) ¹	Specific ²	Total ³	Coeff. (st. err.) ¹	Specific ²	Total ³
Membership (generic)			0.0914 (0.0565)	0.106	n.a.	0.0366 (0.0232)	0.115	n.a.
Morocco	Dir Beni Mellal	ZITOUNE Coop.	0.1196 (0.2136)	0.576	0.179	0.0177 (0.1018)	0.862	0.262
		COLEZA Coop.	-0.0332 (0.2846)	0.907	0.270	-0.0184 (0.1343)	0.891	0.288
	Ait Ouallal Bittit	KHARICHFA Association	0.8855 (0.3604)	0.014 **	0.008***	0.4388 (0.1629)	0.007 ***	0.005 ***
	Kitui	Neema self-help group	0.3602 (0.4502)	0.424	0.180	0.0939 (0.1266)	0.458	0.196
Kenya	Mukurweini	Rugi farmer cooperative society	0.5070 (0.3134)	0.106	0.051 *	0.1995 (0.0838)	0.017 **	0.007 ***
		New gikaru farmer cooperative society	0.1488 (0.2606)	0.568	0.191	0.0312 (0.0717)	0.664	0.208
		Rumukia farmers cooperative society	0.2282 (0.3752)	0.543	0.201	0.0538 (0.0981)	0.584	0.207
		Ruthaka farmers cooperative society	0.1342 (0.2926)	0.647	0.215	0.0675 (0.0833)	0.418	0.151
		Wakulima cooperative society	0.4212 (0.3203)	0.188	0.083 *	0.0563 (0.0816)	0.490	0.175
Tanzania	Kilombero	Kidatu Sugarcane Growers Association	0.0033 (0.2388)	0.989	0.257	0.0211 (0.1227)	0.863	0.2662
	Mvomero	-						
Tunisia	Chebika	GDA Karma	0.1978 (0.2862)	0.490	0.169	0.1687 (0.1199)	0.159	0.072 *
		GDA Jefna	-0.9099 (0.2942)	0.002 ***	0.004 ***	-0.4738 (0.1319)	0.000 ***	0.001 ***
		GDA Ayaycha	0.4928 (0.3830)	0.198	0.090 *	0.2116 (0.1384)	0.126	0.062 *
	Fernana	SMSA	0.1027 (0.3000)	0.732	0.233	0.0247 (0.1136)	0.828	0.259
		GDA Hrayer Gloub Thiren URAP	-0.4284 (0.2196)	0.051 *	0.074 *	-0.0957 (0.0909)	0.292	0.226
			-0.2179 (0.2636)	0.409	0.226	-0.0554 (0.1026)	0.589	0.278
Uganda	Kamuli	Busiba cooperative society	0.4163 (0.5278)	0.430	0.194	0.092 (0.1217)	0.450	0.203
		Kamuli Nankulyaku Maize cooperative	1.1360 (0.4263)	0.008 ***	0.007 ***	0.1333 (0.1221)	0.275	0.145
		Edikokolima Saving and Credit Assoc.	2.6377 (0.9871)	0.008 ***	0.007 ***	0.1324 (0.1273)	0.298	0.153
	Nakaseke	Namasinda kwekulakulanya group	-0.0103 (0.3556)	0.977	0.269	0.068 (0.1276)	0.594	0.232

Nakaseke vegetable producers and seed multiplication association	0.1080 (0.5332)	0.839	0.261	0.0276 (0.1303)	0.832	0.273
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Sample size: 22,645 for the ordered logit and 4,529 for the SEM. ¹ Coefficients and standard from Relation 5. ² *p*-value associated to the coefficients for membership in the specific organizations. ³ *p*-value of a test of joint significance of the generic membership coefficient and the specific coefficient. Significance: * 10% level; **5% level; ***1% level.